

ECONOMICS

PROBLEMS OF REFORMING MUNICIPAL FINANCE IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES: THE CASE OF GEORGIA

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Abstract

This article explores the challenges and solutions in reforming municipal finance in developing countries, with a focus on Georgia's experience. It reviews literature on subnational taxation, fiscal decentralization, and the role of technology in improving fiscal systems. The paper discusses Georgia's legislative framework, budgetary evolution, and governance reforms. Key themes include participatory budgeting, financial management, and the integration of technological innovations like artificial intelligence and green technologies. The findings offer valuable insights for policy and governance in developing nations, emphasizing the need for innovative, collaborative approaches in municipal finance reform.

Keywords: Municipal Finance reforms, Fiscal Decentralization, Public Financial Management, Local Autonomy, Policy and Governance.

Introduction

The endeavor to reform municipal finance in developing countries is a journey fraught with unique challenges and complexities. "Problems of Reforming Municipal Finance in Developing Countries: The Case of Georgia" delves into this intricate subject, using Georgia's experience as a focal point to explore broader themes and lessons that resonate across developing nations.

As Georgia grapples with the nuances of financial reform at the municipal level, it presents a microcosm of the broader struggles and triumphs faced by developing countries in their quest for effective local governance and financial stability. This article seeks to unravel the layers of these challenges, examining the interplay between local realities and overarching economic and political forces that shape the path of fiscal reform.

Through the lens of Georgia's experiences, the article offers a rich exploration of the critical issues and innovative strategies that emerge in the process of overhauling municipal finance systems in a developing country context. It is a narrative that not only illuminates the specificities of Georgia's journey but also provides valuable insights into the universal complexities encountered by countries striving to balance local needs with national priorities in an ever-evolving global landscape.

This exploration is an invitation to understand the multifaceted challenges of municipal finance reform, a subject that is pivotal to the sustainable development and prosperity of communities in developing nations around the world.

Literature review

Bahl and Bird (2008) present a detailed examination of subnational taxation in developing countries, exploring the potential and challenges of implementing effective local tax systems. They argue for the need for more robust and autonomous subnational tax regimes to support decentralized governance. The paper discusses various tax options, including property taxes,

value-added taxes, and excises, considering their appropriateness and efficiency for local governments. This work offers significant insights into fiscal federalism, emphasizing the importance of aligning tax policies with local expenditure responsibilities to enhance fiscal autonomy and accountability in developing regions.

Doran et al. (2022) investigate the influence of broadband coverage and speed on the efficiency of fiscal systems in Eastern European Union countries. The study, conducted through robust regression models, highlights that improvements in broadband infrastructure can positively impact tax collection. This research provides valuable insights into the intersection of technological infrastructure and fiscal policy, indicating that digital advancements can enhance public revenue systems. The findings offer practical implications for policymakers aiming to optimize tax collection through digitalization.

Bahl and Martinez-Vazquez (2022) provide an insightful exploration of fiscal decentralization, delving into its theoretical underpinnings and practical challenges. The article emphasizes the complexity of measuring fiscal decentralization and discusses the impact of decentralization on economic growth, the size of government, governance quality, and equity. The authors highlight the need for a comprehensive and updated database on decentralization, and suggest future research directions. This work is a valuable resource for understanding the multifaceted nature of fiscal decentralization and its implications for policy and governance.

In their extensive survey, Martinez-Vazquez, Lago-Peñas, and Sacchi (2015) offer an in-depth analysis of the impacts of fiscal decentralization. The article comprehensively reviews existing literature to explore how fiscal decentralization affects economic, social, and political outcomes. It discusses the challenges in measuring decentralization, the mixed evidence regarding its impact on economic growth, and its influence on government size and public policies. The authors also

examine the relationship between fiscal decentralization and income inequality, poverty, and regional disparities, offering a nuanced perspective on this complex and multifaceted topic.

Bahl and Martinez-Vazquez's "The Property Tax in Developing Countries: Current Practice and Prospects" (2007) presents an analysis of the role and potential of property tax in developing countries. The front matter of the book, which includes the title, authors, and introductory information, sets the stage for a comprehensive discussion on property taxation. This work is expected to explore the challenges and opportunities of implementing property tax systems in various developmental contexts, providing valuable insights for policymakers and scholars in the field of public finance and taxation.

Katrin Farvac-Vitkovic and Mihaly Kopan's *Municipal Finance: A Guide for Local Government* (2014), published by the World Bank, is an extensive resource. It covers the main aspects of municipal finance: intergovernmental finance; municipal financial management; local revenue; expenditure; and asset and external resource management. This publication aims to guide local governments in improving financial management practices, enhancing transparency, and ensuring sustainable service delivery. It serves as a practical tool for city officials, financial staff, and policy makers to effectively manage municipal finances.

The "Public Financial Management Reform Strategy 2023-2026" delineates the Georgian government's roadmap for enhancing public financial management (PFM) from 2023 to 2026. This strategic document emphasizes the improvement of fiscal policies, efficient utilization of financial resources, and bolstering economic progress. It retrospectively assesses the achievements of preceding strategies and proposes focused objectives in key sectors like budgeting, debt management, and fiscal risk management. The strategy underscores adherence to international standards, fiscal discipline, and augmenting the transparency and efficiency of PFM systems. It also addresses contemporary challenges such as the COVID-19 pandemic and geopolitical tensions, as well as Georgia's ambition to align with the European Union. This document is pivotal for understanding Georgia's fiscal reform trajectory and its response to global economic challenges.

"Fiscal Decentralization and the Challenge of Hard Budget Constraints," edited by Rodden, Eskeland, and Litvack (2003), addresses the complexities of fiscal decentralization in various global contexts. The book explores the tension between local autonomy in fiscal matters and the maintenance of national fiscal discipline. It emphasizes the role of hard budget constraints in preventing local government overspending and examines the institutional frameworks that influence fiscal behavior at subnational levels. This comprehensive work includes case studies from both developed and developing countries, offering valuable insights into the challenges and strategies associated with fiscal decentralization and its impact on macroeconomic stability. The editors provide a nuanced view of fiscal decentralization, considering political, economic, and institutional dynamics, making it a significant resource for

understanding the interplay between local governance and national fiscal policies.

Public Expenditure and Financial Accountability (PEFA) Performance Assessment Report for Georgia's Municipalities (2023) The report provides a thorough assessment of public finance management systems in fifteen Georgian municipalities. Utilizing the 2016 Public Expenditure and Financial Accountability (PEFA) methodology, it evaluates various aspects of fiscal management, uncovering both strengths and weaknesses. Key findings include the robustness of Public Financial Management (PFM) systems and notable variations in performance across municipalities of different sizes. This document is a crucial resource for understanding fiscal governance at the subnational level in Georgia. It offers detailed PEFA scores and rational recommendations for enhancing public financial management."

Municipal Finance and Reforms in Georgia

Historical Context and Territorial Challenges The administrative-territorial arrangement in Georgia has historically been complex and contentious, mainly due to unresolved conflicts in regions such as Abkhazia and Samachablo, following Russian occupation. The Georgian Constitution posits that a definitive territorial arrangement can only be established once the country's full integrity is restored. Despite Georgia being commonly recognized as a unitary state in various legal, political, and scientific discourses, this status remains somewhat ambiguous in current legislation. This is evident from the constitutionally recognized autonomous republics of Adjara and Abkhazia. Normative documents defer the final determination of Georgia's territorial arrangement until after the restoration of territorial integrity, leaving a significant aspect of national governance in a state of flux.

Legislative Framework Governing Local Self-Government

Georgia's governance of local self-government units is underpinned by several key legislative acts:

- The Local Self-Government Code of Georgia
- The Budget Code of Georgia
- The Tax Code of Georgia
- The Law of Georgia on Local Fees
- The Law of Georgia on Grants

These documents collectively establish the fiscal and administrative framework within which local self-governments operate, delineating the scope of their powers and responsibilities.

Municipal Powers and Fiscal Autonomy

Municipal powers, as defined by the Local Self-Government Code, are categorized into 'delegated' and 'own' powers. 'Own' powers are those independently exercised by municipalities, as established by law. In contrast, 'delegated' powers are those conferred by the state or autonomous republics, accompanied by corresponding material and financial support.

Local self-governments in Georgia have broad responsibilities, encompassing crucial financial matters. These include budget preparation and approval, local taxation and fee setting, fund management, and the initiation of various developmental projects. These responsibilities are vital for promoting local economic

growth, employment, tourism, and ensuring effective management of municipal resources and services.

Budget Management and Financial Resources

The Budget Code of Georgia plays a critical role in regulating the administrative aspects of budget management for local governments. It grants local governments autonomy in determining their expenditures, independent of central government directives. The Ministry of Finance of Georgia provides guidelines for budget formulation, presentation, and ratification.

The financial resources of municipalities comprise local taxes, fees, distributions from the value-added tax (VAT), and other revenues as stipulated by Georgian legislation. Notably, the fiscal landscape underwent significant changes post-2019. The system of equalization transfers, which aimed to balance economic disparities across regions, was replaced by allowing local municipalities to retain a portion of VAT revenues – a move signaling a shift towards greater financial decentralization.

Evolution of Municipal Budget Dependence

The reliance of municipal budgets on the central state budget has seen a notable shift. The introduction of additional tax revenues, particularly from the locally retained VAT (19%), has reduced this dependence significantly. In 2015, nearly two-thirds of municipal budgets were sourced from state allocations; by 2022, this figure had decreased to less than a quarter. This evolution marks a significant step in the financial empowerment of local self-governments.

Governance Reforms and Local Democracy Governance structures at the local level have undergone transformative changes. Prior to 2006, local representative bodies had limited functions, with district governors appointed by the president. Post-2006 reforms saw an increase in the powers of the Sakrebulo (local assembly), allowing them to appoint mayors and governors – a measure enhancing local governance. In 2014, further reforms led to the direct election of governors and mayors, thereby increasing local direct democracy. However, these reforms also led to a reduction in the Sakrebulo's influence, and the abolition of local territorial units in favor of the institution of the governor's representative. These changes have posed challenges in local administration and citizen engagement, primarily due to ambiguities in the distribution of rights and responsibilities among various authorities.

Challenges and Potential Solutions in Georgian Municipal Finance

Participatory Budgeting: Initiatives like those in Marneuli and Gori showed promise in democratizing budget processes but faced sustainability issues due to political and financial instability. Ensuring continuous support and engagement is essential.

Open Government Data: Tbilisi and Ajara made strides in enhancing data transparency, but challenges remain in technical implementation, data usage, and completeness. Continuous development and support are needed.

Financial Management: Georgian municipalities are working on improving fiscal responsibility and budgetary control, including public debt management

and revenue optimization. Adapting to economic changes remains a key challenge.

Local Autonomy vs. Central Oversight: Balancing local government independence with national policy compliance is crucial for effective governance and fiscal discipline.

Fiscal Independence: A major issue is limited fiscal independence. Revising tax administration, potentially including income tax retention at the municipal level, could be a solution, inspired by practices in countries like Canada and Germany.

Artificial Intelligence in Finance: Implementing AI offers potential benefits in revenue management and financial transparency but faces challenges in infrastructure, data quality, and ethical considerations.

Green Technologies: Green initiatives face hurdles like high costs, technical challenges, and the need for skilled maintenance. A national policy framework supporting green transformation is essential.

In summary, while Georgia's municipalities face significant challenges in financial management and governance, adopting innovative solutions, revising fiscal policies, and enhancing community engagement could lead to more effective and sustainable local governance.

Conclusion

The journey of reforming municipal finance in developing countries, exemplified by the case of Georgia, is a testament to the resilience and adaptability of local governance structures in the face of evolving challenges. "Problems of Reforming Municipal Finance in Developing Countries: The Case of Georgia" has provided a thorough examination of the multifaceted issues inherent in this endeavor, from participatory budgeting to the integration of technology in fiscal management.

The experiences of Georgia highlight the importance of a nuanced approach to municipal finance reform, one that considers the unique socio-economic and political contexts of each region. The challenges faced in areas such as achieving fiscal independence, balancing local autonomy with central oversight, and adopting new technologies like AI and green initiatives underscore the complexity of this undertaking.

However, the insights gleaned from this exploration are not limited to Georgia. They offer valuable lessons for other developing countries striving to reform their municipal finance systems. The key lies in embracing innovative solutions, continuously adapting policies, and fostering community engagement to navigate the intricate landscape of local governance.

As developing nations, including Georgia, continue on their path to reform, it is crucial to remember that progress is not measured solely in economic terms. The true mark of successful reform is the creation of sustainable, equitable, and resilient communities, where local governments can effectively manage resources to meet the needs of their citizens.

In conclusion, the reform of municipal finance in developing countries is a journey that requires persistence, innovation, and collaboration. By drawing on the lessons learned from diverse experiences and embracing the opportunities presented by new technologies

and approaches, developing countries can pave the way for more effective, transparent, and accountable local governance.

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